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GENERAL INFORMATION

Congress dates

19-21 October 2018/ Sarajevo, B&H
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Language

The official language of the ICCCEB&H 2018 is English

Venue and Registration

Hotel Holiday, Zmaja od Bosne 4, Sarajevo

Registration desk will be open on 19 October 2018 Friday from 8:00 till 17:00 and on 20 October 2018 Saturday from 8:30 till 12:00

KEY TO ABSTRACT IDENTIFICATION

PL	Plenary lecture
OP	Oral presentation
PP-AC	Poster presentation - Analytical Chemistry
PP-IC	Poster presentation - Inorganic Chemistry
PP-BB	Poster presentation - Biochemistry and Biotechnology
PP-PHC	Poster presentation – Phytochemistry
PP-CAM	Poster presentation –Chemistry of Advanced Materials
PP-ENC	Poster presentation – Environmental Chemistry
PP-EDC	Poster presentation – Education in Chemistry
PP-CE	Poster presentation – Chemical Engineering
PP-PTC	Poster presentation – Physical and Theretical Chemistry
PP-OMC	Poster presentation – Organic and Medicinal Chemistry
PP-RC	Poster presentation – Radiochemistry
PP-TRC	Poster presentation – Topics related to Chemistry

A Rare and New Insight into Antidiabetogenic Potential of two *Ganoderma* species: *G. pfeifferi* Bres. 1889 and *G. resinaceum* Boud. 1889 in Alloxan-diabetic Rats

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Oxidative stress

Abstract: Fungal extracts were analyzed spectrophotometrically for the free radicals scavenging activity on 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), superoxide anion (SOA) and nitric oxide radical (NO), as well as for the reducing power activity (FRAP). For determination of bioactive properties of specific compounds present in fungal extracts, the content of total phenols (TP) and flavonoids (TF) were investigated. *G. resinaceum* H₂O extract was found to possess the highest ability to scavenge DPPH[•] and O₂^{•-} (IC₅₀=14.03±0.59 and IC₅₀=29.96±1.19 µg/mL, respectively), while EtOH extract of the same species showed better NO[•] activity (IC₅₀=215.18±1.77 µg/mL). The highest level of TF was found in EtOH extract of *G. pfeifferi* (26.29±0.74 mg QE/g. d.w.), while the highest TP content was determined in EtOH extract of *G. resinaceum* (44.01±0.24 mg GA/g. d.w.). Antidiabetic action of analyzed extracts in treated rats was evaluated by the oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) and histological examination of pancreas and liver in control normoglycemic animals as opposed to animals with alloxan-induced diabetes. Histological examination of pancreatic tissue demonstrated that *G. pfeifferi* extracts have protective effects. On contrary, treatment with *G. resinaceum* H₂O extract showed better action by observing changes in body weight and results of OGTT. Taken all together, analyzed extracts could be considered as a promising candidate for further research with an aim to promote their usage as potential antidiabetic agents, which is for the first time reported for *G. pfeifferi*.

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